

Time-Range Adaptive Processing for Pulse Agile Radar

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Abstract—Some radar systems utilize pulse agility to mitigate interference or synthesize bandwidth. Transmitting different waveforms on a pulse-to-pulse basis can have deleterious effects when traditional pulse-Doppler processing is employed. In this paper a recursive MMSE-based receiver design, denoted as Time-Range Adaptive Processing, is presented. The new method jointly adapts in range and Doppler, thus yielding enhanced sensitivity when compared to adaptation in each dimension separately.

I. INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, pulse Doppler radar systems repeat the same waveform to allow efficient pulse compression and Doppler processing techniques to be used. However, some radars transmit waveforms that change on a pulse-to-pulse basis. Digital technology enables radar systems with narrow instantaneous bandwidths to operate within a wider operational bandwidth and change waveform coding on the fly. Potentially, this agility offers the capability of coexistence among multiple communication and radar systems. Of course, waveform and frequency agility requires more complex processing on reception to achieve the sensitivity of traditional pulse Doppler radar.

In this paper, a new method is proposed that simultaneously estimates the range and Doppler of illuminated scatterers. This approach, entitled Time-Range Adaptive Processing (TRAP), can be viewed as a coupling of the Adaptive Pulse Compression (APC) [1,2] and Re-Iterative Super Resolution (RISR) [3] algorithms when the latter is applied to the slow-time Doppler domain. TRAP employs a minimum mean-squared error (MMSE) framework and is capable of suppressing range and Doppler sidelobes in a pulse agile regime, thus achieving the sensitivity associated with standard pulse-Doppler radar. This method is particularly useful when range-Doppler coupling is inherent to the transmitted pulse train, such as with stepped frequency waveforms [4]. Recently, other model-based approaches have also been considered [5-6], though the sensitivity and operational dynamic range of these methods are unclear.

The pulse compression matched filter in conjunction with traditional Doppler processing performs poorly when pulse agility is employed due to the pulse-to-pulse variations of each waveform's pulse compression output. Hence, a cascaded

approach of APC and RISR will be used as an additional metric for comparison. This approach adapts separately in range and Doppler, whereas TRAP offers a simultaneous approach. Since TRAP, APC, and RISR are all formed using the same mathematical approach, the comparison between TRAP and the APC-RISR combination should highlight the benefits of the coupled domain approach.

II. TIME RANGE ADAPTIVE PROCESSING

A. Signal model

The M transmitted pulses in a single coherent processing interval (CPI) can be represented as the $N \times M$ matrix \mathbf{S} , where the m^{th} column contains the m^{th} length- N discretized waveform. The waveforms in \mathbf{S} may have a different coding, center frequency, or both.

The received signal from the ℓ^{th} range cell and m^{th} modulated pulse \mathbf{s}_m can be denoted as

$$y_m(\ell) = \left[\sum_{\theta} \mathbf{x}^T(\ell, \theta) \mathbf{s}_m e^{jm\theta} \right] + n(\ell), \quad (1)$$

for $m = 0, 1, \dots, M-1$, in which $(\bullet)^T$ is the transpose operator, $\mathbf{x}(\ell, \theta) = [x(\ell, \theta) \ x(\ell-1, \theta) \ \dots \ x(\ell-N+1, \theta)]^T$ is a collection of the complex scattering coefficients associated with the scatterers in the range profile corresponding to Doppler phase shift θ with which the m^{th} waveform convolves at delay ℓ , and $n(\ell)$ is a sample of additive noise.

The collection of N fast-time (range) snapshots of (1) can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{Y}(\ell) = \left[\sum_{\theta} \mathbf{X}(\ell, \theta) (\mathbf{S} \odot \mathbf{V}_{\theta}) \right] + \mathbf{N}(\ell), \quad (2)$$

where

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$$\mathbf{V}_\theta = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & e^{j\theta} & \dots & e^{j\theta(M-1)} \end{bmatrix}$$

is an $N \times M$ matrix,

$$\mathbf{X}(\ell, \theta) = \begin{bmatrix} x(\ell, \theta) & x(\ell-1, \theta) & \dots & x(\ell-N+1, \theta) \\ x(\ell+1, \theta) & x(\ell, \theta) & \dots & x(\ell-N+2, \theta) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x(\ell+N-1, \theta) & x(\ell+N-2, \theta) & \dots & x(\ell, \theta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

is an $N \times N$ matrix containing the scatterer complex amplitudes within $2N-1$ range cells of $x(\ell, \theta)$, and \odot denotes the Hadamard product. The matched filter and TRAP signal models are a reorganized version of (2) which is expressed as the $NM \times 1$ vector

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathbf{y}}(\ell) &= \text{vec}(\mathbf{Y}^T(\ell)) \\ &= \text{vec} \left(\left[\sum_{\theta} \mathbf{X}(\ell, \theta) \mathbf{S} \odot \mathbf{V}_\theta \right]^T \right) + \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\ell), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\ell) = \text{vec}(\mathbf{N}^T(\ell))$. A joint range-Doppler normalized matched filter can be applied to (4) as

$$\hat{x}_{\text{MF}}(\ell, \theta) = \frac{1}{NM} \left[\text{vec} \left([\mathbf{S} \odot \mathbf{V}_\theta]^T \right) \right]^H \tilde{\mathbf{y}}(\ell), \quad (5)$$

in which $(\bullet)^H$ denotes the complex-conjugate transpose (or Hermitian) operator. The TRAP estimate is obtained as

$$\hat{x}_{\text{TRAP}}(\ell, \theta) = \tilde{\mathbf{w}}(\ell, \theta)^H \tilde{\mathbf{y}}(\ell), \quad (6)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}(\ell, \theta)$ is an adaptive filter that is derived in the following section.

B. Time-Range Adaptive Processing

The MMSE cost function for the complex amplitude in the range-Doppler cell corresponding to delay ℓ and Doppler shift θ is given as

$$J(\ell, \theta) = E \left[\left| x(\ell, \theta) - \mathbf{w}^H(\ell, \theta) \tilde{\mathbf{y}}(\ell) \right|^2 \right], \quad (7)$$

where $E[\bullet]$ is the expectation operator and $\mathbf{w}(\ell, \theta)$ is the adaptive filter for the (ℓ, θ) range-Doppler cell. Minimization of (7) with respect to $\mathbf{w}^*(\ell, \theta)$ yields the standard MMSE solution

$$\mathbf{w}(\ell, \theta) = \left(E \left[\tilde{\mathbf{y}}(\ell) \tilde{\mathbf{y}}^H(\ell) \right] \right)^{-1} E \left[x^*(\ell, \theta) \tilde{\mathbf{y}}(\ell) \right], \quad (8)$$

in which $(\bullet)^*$ denotes complex conjugation.

By assuming the range-angle cells are uncorrelated with one another and with the noise, the filter in (8) can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{w}(\ell, \theta) = \rho(\ell, \theta) \left(\sum_{\phi} (\mathbf{R}(\ell, \phi) + \mathbf{R}_n(\ell)) \right)^{-1} \text{vec}([\mathbf{S} \odot \mathbf{V}_\theta]^T), \quad (9)$$

where $\rho(\ell, \theta) = E[|x(\ell, \theta)|^2]$ is the power in the range-Doppler cell at delay ℓ and Doppler shift θ , $\mathbf{R}_n(\ell) = \sigma_n^2 \mathbf{I}_{NM \times NM}$ is the range-Doppler noise covariance matrix if assuming white noise (for noise power σ_n^2), and

$$\mathbf{R}(\ell, \phi) = \sum_{n=-N+1}^{N-1} \rho(\ell+n, \phi) \mathbf{t}_{\phi, nM} \mathbf{t}_{\phi, nM}^H, \quad (10)$$

where

$$\mathbf{t}_{\phi, nM} = \begin{cases} \left[t_\phi(|nM|) \dots t_\phi(NM-1) \mathbf{0}_{1 \times |nM|} \right]^T & \text{for } nM \leq 0 \\ \left[\mathbf{0}_{1 \times nM} \ t_\phi(0) \dots t_\phi(NM-1-nM) \right]^T & \text{for } nM > 0 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

consists of delayed versions of the Doppler-shifted and vectorized transmit matrix \mathbf{S} expressed as

$$\mathbf{t}_\phi = \left[t_\phi(0) \ t_\phi(1) \ \dots \ t_\phi(NM-1) \right]^T = \text{vec}([\mathbf{S} \odot \mathbf{V}_\theta]^T) \quad (12)$$

which corresponds to $n=0$.

A normalization based on [7] is applied to the set of adaptive filters to ensure a constant gain amongst the adaptive filters in (9). The normalized filters are expressed as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{w}}(\ell, \theta) = \frac{\mathbf{w}(\ell, \theta)}{\mathbf{w}^H(\ell, \theta) \text{vec}([\mathbf{S} \odot \mathbf{V}_\theta]^T)}. \quad (13)$$

III. IMPLEMENTATION

TRAP is a recursive algorithm that alternates between estimation of the illuminated scene and estimation of the range-Doppler specific adaptive filters in (13). The implementation of TRAP is depicted in Fig. 1 and discussed in the following. The power estimates in (10) required to compute the adaptive filter weights can be estimated by first applying the matched filter from (5). After constructing an adaptive filter for each range-Doppler cell, the filters are applied to the received signal to obtain an enhanced estimate of the scene. A new set of adaptive filters can be computed based on the enhanced estimate. TRAP alternates between filter and scene estimation until the spectral and range sidelobes are suppressed. The algorithm generally converges after three or four adaptive stages.

Figure 1. Block diagram of TRAP implementation

IV. SEQUENTIAL APC AND RISR

For comparison we implement Adaptive Pulse Compression (APC) [1,2] for range sidelobe suppression and the Re-Iterative Super Resolution (RISR) algorithm [3] for spectral sidelobe suppression. RISR was originally conceived as a means to perform direction-of-arrival estimation. The application of RISR for velocity estimation in a pulse-Doppler regime is outlined below.

The pulse compressed output at the ℓ^{th} range cell of the M pulses, after employing APC, can be denoted as

$$\bar{\mathbf{x}}(\ell) = [\bar{x}_0(\ell) \quad \bar{x}_1(\ell) \quad \cdots \quad \bar{x}_{M-1}(\ell)]^T. \quad (14)$$

Let

$$\bar{\mathbf{V}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 \\ 1 & e^{j\frac{2\pi}{K}} & \cdots & e^{j\frac{2\pi(K-1)}{K}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & e^{j\frac{2\pi}{K}(M-1)} & \cdots & e^{j\frac{2\pi(K-1)(M-1)}{K}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

be a bank of K Doppler steering vectors. The resulting RISR adaptive filter bank is computed as

$$\bar{\mathbf{W}}(\ell) = (\bar{\mathbf{V}}\bar{\mathbf{P}}(\ell)\bar{\mathbf{V}} + \bar{\mathbf{R}})^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{V}}\bar{\mathbf{P}}(\ell), \quad (16)$$

where

$$\bar{\mathbf{P}}(\ell) = \begin{bmatrix} \rho(\ell, 0) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \rho\left(\ell, \frac{2\pi(K-1)}{K}\right) \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

is a diagonal matrix containing the target power in each Doppler bin at the ℓ^{th} range cell and $\bar{\mathbf{R}} = \sigma_n^2 \mathbf{I}_{M \times M}$ is the noise covariance matrix (again assuming white noise). As before, normalization is applied to the adaptive filters as

$$\tilde{\bar{\mathbf{w}}}_q(\ell) = \frac{\bar{\mathbf{w}}_q(\ell)}{\bar{\mathbf{w}}_q^H(\ell)\bar{\mathbf{v}}_q}, \quad (18)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{w}}_q(\ell)$ and $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_q$ are the q^{th} columns of $\bar{\mathbf{W}}(\ell)$ and $\bar{\mathbf{V}}$, respectively. Thus the final range-Doppler estimate is obtained as

$$\hat{x}_{\text{APC-RISR}}(\ell, \theta) = \tilde{\bar{\mathbf{W}}}(\ell)^H \bar{\mathbf{x}}(\ell). \quad (19)$$

In the same fashion as TRAP, the initial power estimates in (17) can be obtained using the Doppler filter bank in (15), after which 10 adaptive iterations are performed.

The combination of APC and RISR is expected to perform well when APC is capable of completely mitigating range sidelobes and RISR is only responsible for reducing the Doppler sidelobes associated with the targets. However, when APC is overwhelmed with a large number of targets at different velocities, the performance will suffer, resulting in some residual range sidelobes. This residue will not be suppressed by the RISR algorithm, which will attempt to suppress the Doppler sidelobes of the targets as well as the Doppler sidelobes of the residue. This lack of degrees of freedom is particularly problematic when pulse agility is employed on transmit due to the resultant range-Doppler coupling.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

Simulation results will be presented to illustrate the benefit of coupled processing using TRAP for pulse agile radar systems. TRAP is compared to standard matched filtering (in range and Doppler) and to the sequential APC-RISR approach described above. The simulation is performed using a stepped-frequency phase-coded waveform. Stepped-frequency waveforms offer the distinct benefit of enhanced range resolution by synthesizing a wide bandwidth with several frequency shifted narrowband waveforms. Coherent processing must be used to realize the improvement in range resolution. The stepped-frequency pulse train consists of $M = 30$ pulses, where the center frequency of the m^{th} pulse is given by

$$f_m = \frac{m}{M-1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{G}\right) = m \frac{3}{116}, \quad (20)$$

for $m = 0, 1, \dots, M-1$ and $G = 4$ is the ratio of the total pulse-train bandwidth to the single-pulse bandwidth. The total bandwidth is 4 times greater than that of a single pulse, yielding a commensurate increase in range resolution when coherent processing is performed. Each pulse consists of a length- $N (= 10)$ chip P4 code [4] which is oversampled by 4 for processing. Figure 2 shows the spectrum of each pulse. Observe that the bandwidth from pulse to pulse has a 90% overlap. Additionally, the waveforms have been bandpass

filtered to emulate the narrow instantaneous bandwidth associated with stepped-frequency radar systems. If the waveforms are not bandlimited, the adaptive algorithms will take advantage of the extraneous bandwidth produced by the phase-coded waveform, though this bandwidth is not available in reality. Note the filtered waveforms are used as the reference waveforms for processing in all cases.

Figure 2. Spectral content as a function of pulse number

The simulation scenario consists of six moving targets for both clutter-free and ground clutter environments. For this case, the transmitted waveforms are length $N=10$ constant-modulus random phase codes, and 30 (M) pulses are employed. The location, Doppler phase, and SNR of the targets are provided in Table 1. Stated SNR values are before a coherent processing gain of 25 dB. Both TRAP and RISR employ 121 Doppler bins distributed evenly between phase angles of $\pm 180^\circ$ for processing resulting in some steering vector mismatch for the targets in Table 1.

TABLE 1. TARGET PARAMETERS

Range Cell	Doppler Phase (deg)	SNR (dB)
196	-100	-5
199	75	5
202	150	-2
205	-130	0
208	50	-10
211	-120	-7

First, the clutter free scenario is examined. Figure 3 displays the standard matched filter (range and Doppler) result in which the target locations are denoted with white circles. The range-Doppler coupling of the stepped-frequency

waveform is evidenced by the spreading of the pulse compression mainlobe near the target locations. Also, range sidelobes appear throughout the image and can be confused with target returns.

Figure 3. Matched filter range-Doppler map (in dB); moving targets are masked by Doppler and range sidelobes

Figure 4 displays the sequential APC-RISR output which has suppressed the range and Doppler sidelobes as well as alleviating much of the coupling. Note that an oversampled version of APC [8] is employed here to enhance the range resolution (*i.e.*, reduce the width of the pulse compression mainlobe) which reduces the Doppler spread at the target locations. This approach performs well here due to the small number of degrees of freedom required to estimate the illuminated scene.

Figure 4. Sequential APC-RISR range-Doppler map (in dB); moving targets at locations are indicated by the white circles

The result after TRAP is applied is shown in Fig. 5. TRAP marginally outperforms the sequential APC-RISR approach as evidenced by the reduction of the range-Doppler coupling. The added complexity of TRAP does not justify the marginal improvement over sequential APC-RISR in this case.

Figure 5. TRAP range-Doppler map (in dB); moving targets at locations are indicated by the white circles

Now consider the previous example with the addition of stationary ground clutter, where the average clutter-to-noise ratio is 40 dB after processing. Note that clutter cancellation, which would be complicated by the pulse-to-pulse frequency agility, is not performed here. The matched filter performs poorly in this scenario, as seen in Fig. 6 where none of the moving targets are visible.

Figure 6. Matched filter range-Doppler map (in dB); moving targets are masked by Doppler and range sidelobes

The sequential APC-RISR approach (Fig. 7) suppresses some of the sidelobes, though only the largest target is identifiable at range cell 199 and Doppler phase angle 75° . This performance degradation is attributed to the limited number of degrees of freedom when adaptation is employed in range and Doppler separately. In Figure 8, the TRAP algorithm uncovers all but one of the masked scatterers (at range cell 208 and Doppler phase angle 50°) by accurately estimating the range-Doppler scene (including the clutter).

Figure 7. Sequential APC-RISR range-Doppler map (in dB); moving targets are masked by Doppler and range sidelobes

Figure 8. TRAP range-Doppler map (in dB); moving targets are revealed at locations indicated by the white circles

Observe the reduction in range-Doppler coupling, indicated by the narrower clutter returns in Figs. 7 and 8, that occurs when sequential APC-RISR and to a greater degree TRAP are employed. This behavior is expected since the RISR algorithm is capable of achieving resolution enhancement depending on the available SNR [2]. Even in the presence of ground clutter the MN degrees of freedom utilized by TRAP are not exhausted. A subspace approach that sacrifices the unused degrees of freedom for a reduction in computational complexity would be more practical.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

A new joint range-Doppler technique called Time Range Adaptive Processing (TRAP) is proposed which is capable of mitigating Doppler and range sidelobes inherent to pulse-agile radar systems. Simulations with TRAP exhibit enhanced sensitivity when compared to the standard matched filter (in range and Doppler) and to the sequential application of adaptive processing in range and Doppler.

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